

Existence Technology, the Future of Cybersecurity

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Abstract

Existence technology creates a state-of-existence in a digital environment to directly assert identity at the point-of authentication. Indirect Assertion of Identity was a compromise of Security Protocol to facilitate adoption of Internet in the 1980's. As the Internet evolved Indirect Assertion became a standard and is looked upon as a given fact. Existence technology looks at not aspect of cybersecurity as a given fact that must be retained.

1. Introduction

Why the Current Cyber Crisis

The current cyber crisis is the result of a misapplication of technology based on a misunderstanding applying security protocols. Much of the current cyber crisis was created by a choice made last century. ANY path forward requires analysis of past decisions. Why were the choices made? Were those decisions correct? Are they still valid?

When secure activity entered the Internet, the digital security theorists fell into three major camps:

Create a parallel Internet for secure activity. This was rejected.

Require a second Factor in addition to data for authentication.

Place a portal to secure services in a public environment.

The overwhelming choice was option 3. Once the choice was made, billions of dollars were spent to mitigate the damage created by this choice. The result of this choice is an environment where data is secure until an attacker arrives. Then security fails.

In order to justify choosing Option 3 marketing was applied making scientifically unsupported claim & falsely claiming functionality. This has exacerbated the problem by giving people unversed in computer science a false sense of security.

The Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) is an example of weakened security passed off as an improvement. It was introduced to harden Access Control in a public environment. In reality MFA is a multiple-step process in which data is gathered. Multi-Factor means two or more unique factors. Data is one factor and no MFA solution can name their alleged Non-Data Factor.

May 11, 2019